

VALUE-BASED MOTIVATIONAL ATTITUDE TOWARDS TRADITIONAL SPORTS GAMES OF TURKIC PEOPLES IN KHOREZM REGION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14282473>

Abstract. *The article provides information about the value-based motivational attitude towards traditional sports games of Turkic peoples in Khorezm region, such as wrestling, kok-boru (a traditional horse game), shooting, horse racing, and games played with music and songs, which are considered some of the most beloved performances of the ethnic community. The research of Uzbek and Soviet scholars, archival data, and documents from Western and Eastern researchers on the emergence, spread, rules, regulations, and timing of traditional sports games of Turkic peoples in Khorezm region are analyzed. The study, based on comparative and analytical methods, reveals the details of these games.*

Keywords: *Turkic peoples, value-based motivational attitude, traditional sports games, wrestling, kok-boru, horse racing, marksmanship.*

Introduction:

Khorezm region, one of the oldest and most vibrant areas of Central Asia, the birthplace of Zoroastrianism, and a region that has played a unique role in the development of science and civilization, with a history stretching over many centuries, holds particular significance due to its history, culture, customs, traditions, attitudes toward values, and their continuity. Its geography, climate, and ecology, especially the people's perspective on the traditional sports games of Turkic peoples, are of special importance.

In this regard, according to the resolution PR-259 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated May 25, 2022, on "Measures to Promote and Develop Ethnosports," the Ethnosport Festival is planned to be held from September 7-10, 2023, at the historical "Ichan Kala" complex in the city of Khiva. During these days, the city of Khiva hosted participants, spectators, and journalists from all over the world in a grand atmosphere.

Furthermore, as a result of the Resolution PR-5149 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated June 17, 2021, on "Measures to Further Develop and Promote Archery," Ziyodakhon Abdusattorov and Amirkhon Sodikov competed in archery at Paris 2024 Summer Olympics, marking the first time archery represented in the event.

Khorezm has long been known as the land of wrestlers. It is the birthplace of Jalaliddin Manguberdi, unrivaled in horsemanship, and Pahlavan Mahmoud, whose back never touched the ground.

Since ancient times, performances at festivals and celebrations in Khorezm region have been organized on a grand scale.

The attitude towards wrestling, one of the traditional sports games of Turkic peoples, stands out with its uniqueness compared to other regions. Information about performances in Khorezm

region was studied by Russian researchers during the time of Tsarist Russia, and these have come down to us in various works.

Analysis of Literature:

T. Kilichev writes, "The Nowruz holiday is not only a New Year celebration but also a celebration of the awakening of nature, the beginning of agriculture, and a festival of labor, which has traditionally been marked in rural areas, especially with great festivities and games. The holiday featured a public fair. In the lush meadows, performances such as ulak (a traditional game), horse racing, and wrestling were organized. Jugglers, jesters, and acrobats demonstrated their arts, adding charm to the celebration."

In Khorezm region, the game called "Kok Buri" in Uzbek, "Ulak" in Karakalpak and Kazakh, and "Gok Boru" in Turkmen, has continued to this day.

According to S.P. Tolstov's information, "The Turkmen custom of "Gok Boru" directly represents the marriage rituals of the tribe, as emphasized by the battle between the Zoroastrian gods, Ahuramazda, the god of good, and Ahriman, the god of evil, which also reflects the relationship between tribes during that period."

Picture 1. "Horse Rider" found near the Bukhara Fortress, 2nd-1st century BC.

I.P. Nebolsin, in his Notes of the Russian Geographical Society, wrote, "On the second day of the holiday, fairs were held in shady and picturesque areas near mosques or cemeteries. Before the fair, various fruits, sweets, and treats were sold. During the fair, the sounds of the trumpet, horn, and tambourine could be heard. Singers sang songs, and dancers performed to the music. There were horse races, wrestlers' fights, bakhshis (singers) duels, as well as performances by acrobats and jesters".

S.P.Tolstov, in his work Ancient Khorezm, noted, "Until the 1920s, the 'Red Rose' holiday in Khorezm was celebrated as a festival of youth, love, happiness, and spring. This holiday began every year on May 13th, with young men and women gathering early in the morning to prepare a bouquet of fresh red roses".

The wrestling performances at Khorezm weddings are also one of the ancient folk theater forms that have survived to this day. In ancient times, people could not fight with others from outside their own fraternity. As in the past, even today, wrestlers do not fight against relatives or clan members, and if they do, they would deliberately surrender out of respect for older individuals, which is evidence of our point.

Picture 2. Wrestlers' Fight (Late 19th Century) - Photo by Kh. Devonov.

In Khorezm, horse racing has firmly established its place in wedding celebrations and public performances. Horses participating in such races are carefully raised from the age of one, trained to run, initially ridden by younger children, and later by older children as they grow stronger. Finally, once they have reached full strength, these horses are added to races.

In 1863, the Hungarian scholar and traveler A. Vambéry, who visited the Khiva Khanate, wrote that despite Khivans being a settled people for several centuries, they still preserved elements of their heroic past in their ceremonies. Horse racing and the struggle for victory were frequent occurrences here. In every large wedding, 9, 19, or 29 horses would race.

According to N. Kalmakov, in the northern districts of Syrdarya region, among Kyrgyz (Kazakh) people, the third or fourth day of the wedding was designated for horse racing. The winners of the race were awarded a horse, money, and sometimes cattle, a cloak, or other goods.

Academician A.N. Samoylovich wrote that at the weddings of Turkmens in the early 20th century, after spectators had watched the horse races and archery contests, they would form a circle with a diameter of five sazhen (1 sazhen = 2.1336 meters) to watch the wrestling, and other performances. This was a unique life-like amphitheater for the steppe, with the first row sitting on the ground, the second row standing, the third-row riding on horses, and the fourth row formed by mounted and camel riders.

Research Methodology:

In general, wrestling, the "golden goblet," archery, horse racing, and games accompanied by music and singing during wedding ceremonies were among the most beloved entertainments of Khorezm people. In Bukhara and Khorezm regions of Uzbekistan, as well as in the western territories of Karakalpakstan, ulak (kopkari) is not played. These regions show a higher interest in horse racing, and the game is organized frequently. This information has also been presented in Russian essays.

Study of archival data, analysis of documents related to the emergence, spread, rules, and timing of traditional Turkish folk sports games in Khorezm region, based on the works of both Western and Eastern researchers, is being conducted through comparative and contrastive methods.

Analysis and Results:

In wrestling, the master of ceremonies announces the name of the wrestler who is challenging for the championship and where they are from. Then, the name of the opposing wrestler is announced. At this time, both wrestlers enter the arena, ready to fight in front of the spectators.

When the organizer gives the command "begin," the two wrestlers approach each other and engage in the match. The wrestler who throws his opponent to the ground, with the opponent's shoulder touching the earth, is considered the winner of the match.

At weddings, several wrestlers pair up and test their strength in the wrestling arena. The wrestler who wins the match usually expresses a desire to continue winning in all the weddings. The first prize is often a horse, the second a piece of leather, and the third, fourth, and fifth prizes are small amounts of money or a scarf.

Spectators would congratulate the victorious wrestlers by lifting them on their horses. The horse would later be given to the winners, while those who remained without horses were congratulated in other ways. Horse racing has long been a popular form of entertainment in Khorezm.

The example given shows that horse racing has been one of the most anticipated spectacles at Khorezm weddings.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it can be seen that the relationship between the people of Khorezm and traditional Turkish folk sports is not a newly forming process. Khorezm, with its rich history, culture, and architecture, has always been influential in Asia and the world. As we discussed above, the people's interest in folk games and sports sets it apart as unique. The Ethnosport Festival held in Khiva from September 7 to 10, 2023, in the historical "Ichan Kala" complex further confirmed the local population's continued interest in these traditional games.

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